

ANO THER CONDITION FOR THE FORMATION OF THE IDEAL PERSON

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Annotation: This article describes how serious the crime of theft is, the issues of pedagogical approach and analysis from a religious point of view when this situation arises.

Key words: sin, right, public good, honest work, veil of modesty, punishment, mercy, wrong companion, punishment for sin, afterlife.

Аннотация Ушбу мақолада ўғирлик қилиш иллати нақадар оғир гуноҳ эканлиги, ушбу ҳолат юз берган вақтда педагогик ёндошув ва диний нуқтаи-назардан таҳлил масалалари баён этилган.

Таянч сўзлар: гуноҳ, ҳақ, ижтимоий таъминот, ҳалол меҳнат, ҳаё пардаси, жазо, меҳр-оқибат, номаъқул ҳамроҳ, гуноҳ, ситам, охират.

Аннотация В данной статье описывается, насколько серьезным является преступление воровство, вопросы педагогического подхода и анализа с религиозной точки зрения при возникновении данной ситуации.

Ключевые слова: грех, право, общественное благо, честный труд, покрывало скромности, наказание, милосердие, неправильный товарищ, наказание за грех, загробная жизнь.

Islam gives the right to live a good life to the people living in the society, regardless of who they are. He brings them up in the right way. It replaces justice in social life. It leaves the door wide open for the honest development of private property. It also organizes the social welfare of the members of the society.

The fact that Islam gives every person the right to live a good life is reflected in the fact that people have good food, clothing, and housing. The main way to

achieve this is the honest work of each person. It is responsible for creating full conditions for the members of the Islamic society to earn with honest work. If a citizen does not have a trade, he teaches a trade. If there is no opportunity or space to realize his craft, he creates that opportunity and space. He will find a job.

Of course, it is not right for people to spend their precious lives in vain.

But there are some people among us who waste their time and spend their precious life in sinful activities. They drink intoxicating drinks and engage in robbery, vandalism and theft. The veil of modesty is lifted from their faces and they lose their honor.

It is said in one Hadith: "Those who misappropriate the wealth of believers will be sent to Hell on the Day of Resurrection."

Al-Faqih Abu Lays As-Samarkandi's work "Tanbehul Ghafilyyn" reads the following sentences about this: "Whoever steals ten dirhams, his hand will be cut off. A Muslim's hand is cut off not because of the ten dirhams, but because of two reasons: because he trampled on the lives of the believers and because he did not agree with what God has distributed. He looked at other people's property. God Almighty commanded to cut him as a punishment for what he did and as an example to those who do not agree with the other distribution of the Creator.

Those who invade, shed others' blood, steal their property, or steal while lying in wait have no right to call themselves believers. Because the religion of Islam calls people to faith and honesty and turns them away from evil and corruption.

Our Prophet Muhammad Mustafa (peace be upon him) used to say: "Cursing a believer is wickedness, and killing him is infidelity." The respect of his wealth is like the respect of his blood, that is, as it is haram to shed his blood, taking his wealth is also haram.

Prophet Akram (peace be upon him) said in a Hadith: "Stealing is a great sin." "Even a person who knowingly buys stolen property is equally guilty of this sin," he said.

Most children steal at least once in their lifetime.

First of all, let's find out what theft is. Theft in Shari'i istilah is the secret taking of someone's hidden property.

By "locked" we mean not unattended. If the warehouse is locked or guarded, the goods are covered. A person who steals an abandoned property will not have his hand cut off, but another measure will be taken. Other measures will be taken against people who leave the closed place, the door of the warehouse is left open and can be seen from it, or who are allowed to walk in and out of the place where the goods are, if they take the goods.

One of the most important conditions is that the property stolen from a hidden place must have the value of a quarter of a dinar during the time of our Prophet (peace be upon him). If it is less than that, the thief's hand will not be cut off. He will be dealt with differently.

Usually, a child likes something very much and he cannot overcome the desire to have that thing. As soon as he receives the item, other feelings appear in him. Owning what he dreams of is only one of these feelings, and besides, the child is tormented by a number of feelings, such as the danger of being caught in an illegal act, the feeling of shame for what he has done, and the fear that his guilt will be exposed. After a while, he realizes that he cannot use the item without telling him where it came from. If the parents are attentive, it will be much more difficult for the child to cope with this task. After some time, they witness the suffering of the owner of the item. He knows well that he is the reason for this. He hears what the people around him are saying in honor of the thief. That person is very afraid that they will find out that it is him. That is why he forms the feeling of not stealing in the child, even if his act is not exposed.

If the theft is discovered, the child will go through the process of investigation, followed by public apologies. All this will be a lesson for his future life. In such cases, it is very important to correctly determine the standard of punishment. On the one hand, the child should feel that he is not looked down

upon, that his sins can be forgiven and that he has not lost trust, and on the other hand, he should also understand the seriousness of his crime.

Some children steal more than once. Such children include mostly neglected children. They do not expect any affection from those around them. Such children think that they have nothing to lose in front of people, and consider their theft undetected as luck. They plan the theft carefully. They take all precautions to avoid being caught in the wrong. They find reasons and excuses for what they have acquired. They don't get into trouble for trivial things.

Some children steal and take revenge on their parents for neglecting them. Such cases often occur in families where parental feelings are displayed in people, but the real situation is the opposite. Children in such families feel like a strange crocodile in a cage. By committing theft, they seem to be giving a warning to those around them: "Everything is not as good as you think, they are deceiving you, help me." This warning is also directed at parents, meaning, "If you don't stop being hypocritical, I will expose you and not allow you to be a hypocrite."

In such cases, parents should reconsider their relationship with their children. Stealing as revenge can be directed not only at parents, but also at others. For example, if a child asks for something he likes for a while and receives a refusal: "I asked you, and you are hot." So here's to you!" acts as if.

Wise men say: "Whosoever sows the tree of pain and reproach, he will reap the fruit of pain and suffering." Let's give an example of this story: One day Wealth, Knowledge and Honor met. Wealth said: "If I get lost, look for it in the market and labor, and look for knowledge in mosques and madrasahs." "If I get lost," said Honor, "don't bother looking for me, you won't find me anywhere..."

In fact, it is unlikely that people who have lost their honor and tarnished their honor will be able to restore their former rank and position. It will be a black mark in their life. Everyone avoids a person who has been caught stealing. The name thief is always attached to his name like a curse. While everyone lives in

peace and tranquility, the thief lives in constant danger, suffering, and shelter. Because of his wickedness, people are troubled.

Rasul Akram (may God bless him and grant him peace) said about such people: "On the Day of Judgment, the lowest rank of people is the one who is disturbed by his badness in the world."

Thefts can become normal for the child. Such incidents happen more often in boys and girls who do not openly express their displeasure. They look for a reason to vent their pent-up bad moods, and this often manifests itself in theft or other similar situations (for example, damaging the "culprit's" property). If the child is taught to properly express his feelings of displeasure, then the tendency to steal will gradually decrease and disappear by itself.

Adolescent children may also commit theft at the behest of their companions. At this time, it is seen to separate children from undesirable companions.

Stealing can be an interesting activity for an idle child who has nothing to do. Such children usually do not know what to spend their energy on. It is said about them, "They are full of joy." The best way to "treat" such children is to get them out of greed and let them get what they want only through their own hard work. What can be concluded about the cases of child rearing and theft?

Parents should not pay attention to the things that appear in their children. They should not be allowed to appropriate what they have "found". It is better to identify the places where you find them and hand them over to a teacher, guard or someone in charge. A child cannot be unjustly accused of theft. It is reasonable to accept his words as true.

If a child's theft is discovered, he should be punished. Punishment should be serious, it should not be physical, and it should be a reason to not repeat such acts. It is necessary to avoid breaking the child's psyche by increasing the standard of punishment. After the child has served the punishment, it is necessary to forget about this incident and not return to it again. If the theft is repeated, it is necessary

to carefully study the current situation and to prevent it, in addition to punishing the child, it is necessary to eliminate the reasons that caused the theft. If there is no valid reason for the theft, or if the factors used do not work, it is better to contact the experts before irreparable mistakes are made. It will be much more difficult to correct a state of chronic moral deviation. A psychologist is consulted first. If necessary, he should be recommended to see a psychoneurologist and a psychiatrist.

In addition to this, it is necessary to try to explain correctly from the religious point of view, based on the fact that this family is Muslim, so that it is necessary to explain long before this incident that stealing a child is a very serious sin and that it is inevitable to answer for it in front of Allah on the Day of Judgment. If the child is involved in this bad business for some reason, it is necessary to find a way to his heart without regretting it. It is necessary to explain that God created us in this world for testing and that the real life is still ahead and that there is a way to make this life beautiful and to forgive the mistakes and sins. For example

Islamic society educates its members on the right path. Their education is built on the basis of faith, fear of God, and hope for the Day of Resurrection. It is deeply explained that it is the duty of every Muslim to find and eat sustenance in a halal way. It is explained that theft is a sin, that it is a sin to eat someone else's property by false means, and that a thief is a sinner.

... In one story it is written: "There was a dervish. He was called Donadil because he was cheerful, polite and wise. One day, Donadil goes on a pilgrimage to Mecca. On the way, a few robber invaders blocked his way, thinking that he must have a lot of wealth. Then Donodil said: "I have no wealth." I only have a bed that I have taken. If you want it, take it. But leave me alone, let me live my dream."

The thieves ignored his words and drew their swords to kill him. Donodil was confused and looked around. At that time, he noticed a flock of wild ducks flying overhead. Donodil looked at them and said: "Hey, ducks, I fell into the

hands of criminals in this wilderness." You bear witness to my case and punish these people."

But the thieves made fun of him and killed him laughing... The news of Donadil's death reached the ears of the city residents. They started looking for the killers.

One day, people gathered in the mosque to pray. Donodil's killers - thieves were also sitting in one corner. Suddenly, a flock of wild ducks flew down from the sky and circled around the thieves. At that time, one of the thieves sarcastically said to his accomplice: "They are demanding Donodil's funnel." The man who heard this said it to his companion, and he told another one. So this news reached the ears of the mayor. They immediately caught the thieves and punished them.

So, we as parents and teachers should be very careful about the evil of theft, because it can cause the servant to fall into a miserable situation on the Day of Judgment.

... People who engage in theft and robbery will be disgraced in the Hereafter. May Allah protect us all from this error.

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